

Micro-computed tomography imaging of acellular or cellular hydrogels and organ-on-a-chip platforms

Jana Vecstaudza, Karina Egle, Abhishek Indurkar, Janis Locs

Rudolfs Cimdins Riga Biomaterials Innovations and Development Centre of RTU, Institute of General Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Materials Science and Applied Chemistry, Riga Technical University, Pulka 3, Riga, LV-1007, Latvia

*Baltic Biomaterials Centre of Excellence Headquarters, Riga, Latvia
e-mail: jana.vecstaudza@rtu.lv*

Organ-on-chip (OOC) platforms are a cutting-edge approach for studying tissue physiology and disease modeling in a physiologically relevant context. Usually as different tissue mimics within the OOCs hydrogels are used. However, when hydrogel-filled OOCs are imaged using micro-computed tomography, the contrast of the images is low. Therefore, this study aims to screen possible staining agents for x-ray contrast improvement of such hydrogels.

In the study, 10 wt.% Gelatin methacryloyl (GelMA)¹ acellular or cellular hydrogels were used. Cellular hydrogels were with MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts (1×10^6 cells/mL). Crosslinking was done using UV ($\lambda=365$ nm, 5 min, *Irgacure 2959*). Then, the following staining agents were used: lead acetate, phosphotungstic acid, barium chloride, potassium iodide, Lugol's iodine, iron (III) oxide, ammonium monovanadate, ammonium molybdate, and sodium tungstate. Micro-CT imaging was done with μ CT 50 instrument (Scanco Medical, CH).

Results of the study showed increased X-ray contrast for GelMA hydrogels treated with staining agents compared to untreated (Fig. 1). In most cases, uniform staining was obtained.

Figure 1. 2D micro-CT image slices show increased X-ray contrast of GelMA hydrogels stained with different staining agents for 24 h (2% w/v).

Overall, our approach successfully demonstrated the capabilities of the non-destructive visualization of hydrogels using micro-CT analysis with varying x-ray contrasting agents. This study paves the way for more comprehensive studies of cell-hydrogel interactions.

Acknowledgments. The authors acknowledge European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under grant agreement No. 953121 (FLAMIN-GO) for the funding and access to infrastructure and expertise of the BBCE - Baltic Biomaterial Centre of Excellence (European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 857287).

References

1. Van Den Bulcke A.I.; Bogdanov B.; De Rooze N.; Schacht E.H.; Cornelissen M.; Berghmans H. *Biomacromolecules*. **2000**, *1* (1), 31-38.